

Master's Programme in Advanced Energy Solutions- Energy Conversion Processes

Heat transfer in intensified synthesis reactors

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Abstract

This study investigates the heat transfer characteristics of various geometries—including diamond cells, TPMS (Triply Periodic Minimal Surface), and monolith structures—within a packed bed reactor. The literature review presents an overview of catalytic methanol production via CO₂ hydrogenation, emphasizing the role of structured metallic designs, such as honeycomb monoliths, foams, and Periodic Open Cellular Structures (POCS), in enhancing reactor performance. By focusing on process intensification within catalytic reactors, this study evaluates the effect of structured packed bed characteristics on heat transfer.

During the experimental phase, several POCS lattice structures, primarily diamond cells and multiple TPMS geometries, were fabricated and dedicated heat transfer tests in a non-reactive setup were performed. Heat transfer was evaluated using a one-dimensional model to assess the influence of lattice structure, cell size, porosity, and wall contact on the air-side heat transfer coefficient. This study demonstrates that TPMS structures, particularly the diamond matrix, offer superior heat transfer performance compared to POCS structures and other TPMS geometries, such as the gyroid matrix. Smaller cell sizes within these structures further enhance heat transfer efficiency, making them ideal for optimizing thermal management in small-scale, distributed chemical production systems.

Keywords Process Intensification, heat transfer, methanol synthesis, CO₂ hydrogenation, POCS, TPMS

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Preface and acknowledgements

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Otaniemi, 26 December 2024
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Symbols and abbreviations

Symbols

c_p	Heat capacity of the gas [J/kg K]
d_{cell}	POCS cell diameter [m]
$d_{particle}$	Diameter of particles [m]
d_s	POCS strut diameter [m]
d_t	Diameter of the reactor [m]
d_{wall}	Thickness of the reactor wall separating the oil and air [m]
d_{window}	POCS window diameter [m]
G	Specific mass flow rate [kg/m ² s]
$h_{w,packing}$	Heat transfer coefficient of the packing [W/m ² K]
$h_{w,structure}$	Heat transfer coefficient of the metallic structure [W/m ² K]
k_{gas}	Thermal conductivity of the gas [W/m K]
$k_{particle}$	Thermal conductivity of the particles [W/m K]
$k_{solid,structure}$	Thermal conductivity of the metallic structures [W/m K]
$k_{eff,packing}$	Effective thermal conductivity of the packing [W/m K]
$k_{eff,structure}$	Effective thermal conductivity of the structure [W/m K]
k_{wall}	Thermal conductivity of the reactor wall [W/m K]
Pe_{rif}	Radial Peclet Number in packed bed [-]
Pr	Prandtl Number [-]
R_{IF}	Heat transfer resistance between packing and structure [K m ² /W]
R_{INT}	Concentrated internal heat transfer resistance [K m ² /W]
R_p	Internal heat transfer resistance of the packing [K m ² /W]
$R_{structure}$	Internal heat transfer resistance of the structure [K m ² /W]
R_{wall}	Concentrated heat transfer resistance at the wall [K m ² /W]
Re	Reynolds number [-]
Re_p	Particle Reynolds number [-]
$S_{v,structure}$	Specific Surface Area of structure [1/m]

T_c	Bulk mean temperature [°C]
T_{oil}	Wall temperature [°C]
U_{air}	Heat transfer coefficient on the air side [W/m ² K]
U_{oil}	Heat transfer coefficient on the oil side [W/m ² K]
$U_{overall}$	Overall heat transfer coefficient [W/m ² K]
$U_{structure \rightarrow Packing}$	Heat transfer coefficient between structure and packing [W/m ² K]
u	Superficial Gas Velocity [m/s]
$V_{particle}$	Volume occupied by particles [m ³]
$V_{structure}$	Volume occupied by the metallic structure [m ³]
V_{total}	Total volume of the reactor body [m ³]
V_{void}	Volume of the remaining voids after the particles [m ³]
z	Axial position [m]
$\varepsilon_{packing}$	Porosity of the packing pattern [-]
$\varepsilon_{structure}$	Porosity of the metallic structure [-]
ε_{total}	Total porosity [-]
ρ_{gas}	Density of the gas [kg/m ³]

Abbreviations

AM	Additive Manufacturing
CPI	Channels Per Square Inch
OFA	Open-Frontal Area
POCS	Periodic open cellular structures
PPI	Pores per linear inch
TPMS	Triply Periodic Minimal surfaces

1 Introduction

The climate target of limiting the global temperature increase to 2 °C above pre-industrial levels, agreed upon by 190 nations during the Paris Agreement in 2015, has initiated a paradigm shift towards exploring technologies to reduce our dependence on fossil fuels and greenhouse gas emissions [1]. This goal can be achieved by finding alternative technologies and reducing energy consumption through improved process efficiencies. Consequently, the scientific community is exploring technologies that reduce or even utilize atmospheric carbon dioxide, a major greenhouse gas, to achieve carbon neutrality quickly. Concurrently, with growing interest in green hydrogen, synthetic fuels such as e-methanol are gaining prominence in research and development.

In recent years, much work has been done towards studying methanol production through carbon dioxide hydrogenation and multiple large-scale prototypes have been established over time [2]. These processes can be further improved by optimizing energy consumption and enhancing heat and mass transfer to achieve higher throughput. The size of the chemical process can significantly impact energy consumption, and often large-scale processes can be less energy efficient [3]. Furthermore, given that renewable energy sources are geographically dispersed and decentralized, there is a necessity for small-scale methanol production processes to be located nearby. According to Braconi, process intensification is the path to follow when developing small and efficient processes [4]. With intensification, process costs decrease as sizes become smaller through higher space utilization but at the same time the fluid behaviour within the equipment also changes, consequently, the design of the equipment must be even more intentional. To achieve maximum conversion in a catalytic reactor, the reactor internals are designed to increase the exposed surface area for the reaction. The design of the catalyst supports impacts the fluid flow and the interaction between different components, thereby affecting the pressure drop, heat and mass transfer, and overall reaction conversion.

This thesis studies the heat transport properties of several structured catalyst in packed bed reactors focusing on their specific properties through a series of experiments. The influence of the material of these structures and other physical properties namely cell type, cell size, porosity, etc. are thoroughly examined. Structured catalysts play a crucial role in industrial chemical processes, as they impact both the efficiency and effectiveness of the catalytic reactions by affecting the heat transfer characteristics within the reactor.

To conduct this study, methanol synthesis is chosen as the basis. This selection is due to the complex reaction kinetics involved in methanol production, which include both exothermic and endothermic reactions. The

presence of these opposing reactions creates a challenging environment for heat transfer analysis, making it an ideal model for this research.

The primary aim of this thesis is to explore the heat transfer characteristics of various structured catalyst supports within packed bed reactors, particularly focusing on configurations that enhance thermal management in a catalytic reactor. Through systematic investigation with diverse lattice geometries—including diamond cells, TPMS (Triply Periodic Minimal Surface) structures, and monoliths—the study investigates how factors such as cell type, cell size, porosity, and material composition influence the overall heat transfer performance. In the experimental phase, this research conducts non-reactive heat transfer tests across various conductive structures designed to intensify heat transfer in fixed bed catalysts. These tests aim to isolate and understand the influence of lattice structure, wall contact, and material composition on heat transfer, helping to identify configurations that optimize thermal efficiency.

Although methanol synthesis is the specific focus of this study, the findings and methodologies developed are designed to be broadly applicable. The insights gained from this work are expected to contribute to a framework for designing efficient, small-scale catalytic reactors suited to decentralized and sustainable chemical production, beyond just methanol synthesis. By refining heat transfer principles, the findings can be broadly applied across other catalytic processes where enhanced thermal management is crucial, supporting both cost-effective and eco-friendly industrial applications.

2 Methanol Synthesis

Methanol is a valuable precursor for production of various chemicals and can also be used as a transportation fuel. As a result, there is a lot of research ongoing towards carbon dioxide and hydrogen as feedstock for methanol production.

2.1 Reactions for methanol production

Traditionally, the methanol is produced in two steps: i) production of syngas through steam methane reforming or gasification ii) Methanol synthesis from CO. Coal gasification is also gaining momentum for methanol production in last few years [5].

The newer technologies apply hydrogenation of carbon dioxide in order to produce methanol. There are three reactions involved in the methanol synthesis which are as follows: Carbon dioxide hydrogenation, carbon monoxide hydrogenation and reverse water gas shift reaction [6].

The above reactions are also involved in the conventional methanol manufacturing processes, however, traditionally, the amount of carbon monoxide is higher in the syngas compared to carbon dioxide. The enthalpy values for each reaction are provided at a temperature of 25 °C and 1 bar pressure [7]. The equation (3) is the reverse water gas shift reaction which produces carbon monoxide and water while reducing the methanol selectivity.

Depending on the operating conditions inside the reactor, the reactions can proceed in either direction. Reaction enthalpies for equation (1) & (2) indicate that the reactions are exothermic, and the number of moles reduce in the forward direction, however, the reverse water gas shift reaction (3) is endothermic in nature. Therefore, as per Le Chatelier's principle, for methanol synthesis, the favourable conditions would be low temperatures and high pressures. Based on industrial practices, a temperature of 200-250 °C and 50-100 bar is maintained to achieve the conversion [5].

These reactions are promoted in the presence of a catalyst as they are very slow to occur on their own. Typically, a Cu/Zn/Al₂O₃-based catalyst is used for the reactions [8]. At lower temperatures, the rate of reaction is slow. As

the temperature increases, the molecular kinetic energy also rises, increasing the rate of reaction. Therefore, to achieve a higher rate of reaction, the operating temperature should be higher. However, if the temperature is increased too much, the reverse water-gas shift reaction would become dominant and consume the hydrogen molecules present in the reaction mixture. Because of the high exothermicity of methanol production reactions and endothermicity of the side reactions, adequate control of the reactor temperature becomes highly crucial for more conversion to methanol [9]. To minimize the loss of unconverted reactants and achieve higher overall methanol conversion, a recycling stream is necessary. Consequently, many conventional methanol processes have recycle streams to achieve higher conversion. To promote the production of methanol, an optimum temperature must be maintained, and the reactor design must consider effective heat transfer.

When the feedstock for methanol synthesis is modified to pure carbon dioxide and hydrogen, the reaction chemistry reduces to reaction (1) and (3). In this case, the reactions can occur at a lower temperature providing a better control over side reactions [10].

2.2 Industrial Reactors for methanol production

There are several designs for methanol reactors in the industry, classified into gas and liquid phase reactors [8]. Among these, gas phase reactors are more prevalent in methanol production. They can be adiabatic or nearly isothermal, primarily differing in the cooling systems used for heat removal.

Adiabatic reactors can be designed as quench reactors, which consist of multiple adiabatic beds. Temperature control in these reactors is achieved through direct or indirect cooling which are shown in the Fig 1. below. Direct cooling involves introducing cold feed gas at different levels within the reactor beds, which reduces the temperature following the exothermic reaction. Indirect cooling employs interstage heat exchangers or an external jacket with a cooling water supply. The purpose of quench reactors is to manage the heat generated during the reaction effectively [8].

Figure 1 a) Direct Cooling with cold feed gas b) Indirect cooling with interstage cooler and c) External supply of cooling water [8]

Another popular reactor design available is quasi-isothermal steam raising fixed bed reactors which was first given by Lurgi [5]. Reactor designed by Lurgi (Figure 2.a)) is a tubular reactor which are filled with catalyst and gas flows axially through the narrow tubes. The shell side is filled with boiling water which is then converted to medium/high pressure steam as the reaction proceeds which provides a tight temperature control. These reactors seem to outperform quench reactors in terms of better heat removal and more control of the temperature due to higher gas velocities through the narrow tubular design. There are other major licensors for similar technological design are Johnson Matthey Davy Technologies, Linde & Haldor Topsoe.

Other designs involve maintaining radial gas flow across the catalyst bed within the reactor as shown in Figure 2.b). This design can result in a lower pressure drop, which is advantageous for scaling up production capacity.

Figure 2 a) Lurgi, b) Radial flow, c) Methanol Casale and d) Lurgi MegaMethanol [5]

Methanol Casale has developed a pseudo-isothermal methanol converter reactor that utilizes cooling via feed, boiling water, or both simultaneously.

The cooling setup, as described in Figure 2.c), is arranged inside hollow plates filled with the catalyst [11], allowing for more stringent temperature control due to the axial-radial flow configuration.

Liquid phase reactors, including trickle bed reactors and slurry reactors, are increasingly being used for methanol production. These reactors offer more reliable temperature control and higher heat transfer but have a complex design compared to fixed bed reactors. They feature a fixed bed of catalyst with co-current gas-liquid flow, and as the reaction progresses, the methanol produced is absorbed into the liquid phase, promoting the forward reaction [8]. A liquid phase reactor developed by Air Products, utilised an inert mineral oil as the liquid for suspending fine catalyst particles allowing better temperature control.

Some technologies tend to combine the gas-cooled reactors and boiling water reactors to achieve a higher conversion in single pass. Lurgi designed the combined pass reactor called as Lurgi MegaMethanol as illustrated in the Figure 2d. for higher production of methanol. The gas feed is preheated in the gas-cooled reactor cooling down the reactor, and goes on to the boiling water reactor, where some conversion takes place. The heat from the reaction mixture is recovered by generating steam on tube side. The gas mixture from the outlet of boiling water reactor, enters the catalyst side of the gas-cooled reactor for further conversion. The heat recovery in this hybrid reaction setup is higher which provides higher temperature management.

2.3 Intensified Catalytic Reactors

Besides conventional reactor designs, intensified reactors have been investigated especially because of their theoretically proven application in small to medium scale plants [12]. These theoretical benefits stem from the fact that intensified reactors have not yet been extensively tested or validated at an industrial scale. Scaling down reactor designs for small-scale applications presents numerous challenges due to the reduced size of the equipment. These challenges often include a higher pressure drop across the reactor, which can affect efficiency and require more energy for fluid movement. The direct miniaturization of commercial scale reactor design is not feasible as the small size can also lead to the generation of hot spots, where localized temperature spikes occur, potentially impacting reaction kinetics and catalyst performance. Furthermore, downscaling is mainly a cost issue that prevents advanced reactor designs from being used in small-scale applications, as the high costs associated with advanced technologies and materials are not economically feasible for smaller operations.

Process intensification, as described by the European Roadmap of Process Intensification (2007), involves the application of innovative principles in process and equipment design to achieve substantial improvements in efficiency, cost, quality, waste reduction, and safety. One method under extensive research is the use of structured catalyst supports, which aim to enhance the interaction between reactants and catalysts. Various structured packings are also being studied to optimize heat and mass transfer, utilizing different lattice topologies and materials. In case of methanol synthesis, the conversion is very temperature sensitive and in a compact reactor design temperature control measures become even more critical to have high conversion rate. Chapter 3 will discuss more about various catalyst supports.

3 Catalyst Supports

In case of catalytic reactors, based on the enthalpy of the reaction, the heat transfer must take place towards or away from the reaction zone i.e., if the reaction is endothermic the heat must be added to the system and if the reaction is exothermic, the heat generated must be removed [13]. As discussed earlier, multitubular packed bed reactors have shown promising utility in the industry because of good temperature control. Even with advanced design of these reactors there are challenges which limit the quality of the heat transfer and problems such as hot spots and runaway reactions may arise.

In the reactor tubes, convective heat transfer is more significant than conduction because conduction relies on effective contact between the reactor wall and catalyst particles, which is often inadequate [9]. Therefore, for enhanced heat transfer, longer tubes with small diameter are used to ensure adequate contact between the wall and catalyst for improved conversion. However, this design choice necessitates reactors frequently operate at lower throughput to avoid equipment damage and excessive by-product formation. While alternative reactor designs have been explored to address these issues, the solution may lie in structured fixed beds using different catalyst supports. In order to limit the effects of thermal shocks in case of highly exo/endothermic catalytic reactions, metallic monolithic catalysts have shown to be beneficial [14].

3.1 Metallic structures

The following discussion will concentrate on monolithic three-dimensional metallic structures and supports for catalysts, encompassing honeycomb monoliths, foams, and periodic open cellular structures. These structures can either be coated with a thin catalyst layer or the voids packed with catalyst. Coated catalysts have their own drawbacks in terms of constraints in the coating techniques and small catalyst inventory due to thin catalyst coating needed for the process. As a result, packing these metal structures with the catalyst would not only eliminate the limited catalyst inventory problem but simplify the catalyst loading and unloading process in line with industrial practices. Therefore, this thesis examines the heat transfer behaviour for the latter.

3.1.1 Honeycomb Monoliths

Honeycomb monoliths consist of numerous narrow, thin-walled parallel channels through which reactants flow and reactions occur. These channels

can have simple or complex shapes, including square, triangular, or hexagonal cross-sections. Traditionally, honeycomb monoliths have served as coated catalyst supports [15]. However, due to the limited catalyst inventory with these techniques, these structures can also be used with packed catalysts to improve effectiveness, as demonstrated by approaches involving small catalyst particles packed within the structured supports [16],[17].

Honeycomb monoliths are thermally and mechanically connected and are characterized by Channels Per Square Inch (CPSI) and Open-Frontal Area (OFA) [14]. CPSI determines the size of the channels in the structures while OFA is the ratio of the gas flow area to the total cross-sectional area of the monolith. These structures are known for high void fraction and high geometric surface area but because of the channels there is no lateral mixing. Honeycomb monoliths outperform randomly packed beds by ensuring a uniformly distributed flow of reactants and products through their channelled paths. In many reactors, the flow becomes laminar due to the low Reynolds number and the channel distribution, resulting in a pressure drop that is reduced by two orders of magnitude compared to packed beds [18]. Because of this, these structures have been used in various environment protection processes, for example, exhaust gas treatment, catalytic combustion and several gas to liquid processes.

Generally, honeycomb monoliths structures, when made of ceramics, have limited heat transfer in radial direction and are not effective in non-adiabatic reactor conditions [15]. However, if the material is metallic, conductive properties of metal can improve the heat transfer in the radial direction which open wider opportunities for honeycomb monolithic structures for cases where stringent temperature control is needed.

3.1.2 Foams

According to Sinn et al., open-cell foams have been extensively studied as coated catalyst supports in catalytic reactors with temperature-sensitive reaction kinetics due to their excellent heat transfer properties, low pressure drop, and high radial mixing [19]. However, recently, their utility as packed catalysts has also been extensively investigated, surpassing that of honeycomb monoliths.

Foams are irregular structures created by trapping air or gas particles within a solid or liquid medium, and they are known for being highly porous materials. These are mainly classified as open-cell foams and closed-cell foams. In open-cell foams, the cells are interconnected by ligaments called struts, forming a network, whereas in closed-cell foams, each cell is isolated

and not connected to other pores and therefore, closed-cell foams have not been explored for their use as structured catalysts.

In the context of open-cell foams, the term pores per linear inch (PPI) is used to describe the foam structure in the industry which is the number of pores present in the area of square inch. Other properties such as cell size, pore size, strut diameter, and porosity (highlighted in Fig. 3.) are also considered during the design and characterization of foam structures [18]. Generally, open-cell foams exhibit good mechanical strength and have a high specific surface area, making them lightweight but stable. The high porosity of open-cell foams results in a lower pressure drop through the reactor.

Figure 3. Cell structure of an open cell foam [18]

The irregularity and interconnections between the cells in open-cell foams generally allow fluid to flow in all directions, enabling enhanced fluid mixing. As a result, open-cell foams exhibit greater heat and mass transport in the radial direction, even better than honeycomb monoliths [14]. When the material of the foams is changed from ceramics to a highly conductive metal, such as copper or aluminium, then the heat transfer in the radial direction is further improved due to high thermal conductivity which makes it significantly better than that in packed bed reactors. Unlike packed bed reactors, in case of packed foams it is essential to consider the ratio of catalyst particle diameter to window diameter, which is the opening or gap between adjacent struts within a cell, when determining the amount of catalyst to fill within the structure.

In 2018, Fratolocchi utilized metal open-cell foams in an intensified Fischer-Tropsch process within a multitubular packed bed reactor [20]. The study demonstrated that these foams offered superior control over the reactor's internal temperature, allowing for operation within a narrow temperature range—something not feasible with conventional packed bed reactors.

Despite all their benefits, foams lack uniformity in cell size, pore size and strut diameter. The irregularity within the foam structure complicates the development of heat and mass transfer models for studying their behaviour. As a result, many correlations developed for investigating the behaviour of foams is based on simplified portrayal of foam geometry.

3.1.3 Novel Structures

With the rising popularity of additive manufacturing, the development of intricate lattice structures has become feasible. Periodic open cellular structures (POCS) are novel frameworks that are gaining popularity due to the advancements and capabilities of additive manufacturing (AM). POCS are regular frameworks created by replicating a unit cell structure. These structures are being studied as they utilise the structured approach of honeycomb monoliths and properties of open-cell foams such as mechanical strength and radial heat transport [21]. They utilise the basic unit cell, for example, cubic cell, diamond cell or tetrakaidecahedra cell (Kelvin cell) and are reproduced in all spatial directions to achieve the final structure.

The properties of Periodic Open Cellular Structures (POCS) are characterized by factors such as Cells per Inch (CPI), cell topology, cell size and angle, strut diameter, and window diameter. By modifying these geometric dimensions, properties like void fraction, packing efficiency can be altered and their effects can be noticed. Numerous research opportunities exist in studying POCS properties, as variations in the initial cell design can significantly influence factors such as heat and mass transfer, pressure drop, and overall performance characteristics.

Additive manufacturing, commonly known as 3D printing, plays a crucial role in the development and production of POCS. AM allows for precise control over the geometry and dimensions of lattice structures, facilitating the design of custom structures with high strength-to-weight ratios and excellent thermal management. For instance, AM enables the creation of honeycomb monoliths, open-cell foams, and POCS with controlled porosity and tailored properties.

Despite the advantages, 3D printing faces challenges such as high costs and limitations in printing size. However, its ability to produce complex unit cells optimized for specific mechanical or thermal properties makes it indispensable for advancing the study and application of POCS. The following figures (Fig. 4.) illustrate various cellular structures, showcasing the design flexibility and potential of AM in this field.

Figure 4. a) Cubic Cell b) Diamond cell & c) Tetraikaidhedra cell

TPMS (stands for Triply Periodic Minimal surfaces) are structures whose geometry can be defined mathematically for having zero mean curvature at all points on the surface, therefore, do not have any edges or corners [22]. These structures can be easily described mathematically through trigonometric functions. In the past decade, TPMS structures have gained much attention for their mechanical and thermal properties and their application as catalyst supports where strict temperature management is needed.

Figure 5. a) Gyroid Sheet b) Diamond Sheet & c) Diamond Skeleton

The consistent and regular pattern of lattice structures in POCS ensures stable investigative models, unlike the deviations often noted in open-cell foams. However, the complexity of these models can vary depending on the specific lattice structure. For instance, a heat transfer model for TPMS structures would be significantly more complex than one designed for cubic cell structures.

3.2 Comparison with randomly packed bed

Figure 6 illustrates the benefits of the coated catalyst structures compared to the commercially prevalent regular packed bed configuration. Typically, the flow pattern is cross-mixed, except in the case of honeycomb

monoliths. In contrast, flow in normal packed bed reactors can become non-uniform and unevenly distributed due to the channelling effect, particularly near the walls, which significantly impairs heat transfer between the packing and the reactor wall [23]. Randomly packed beds may also experience some tortuosity, leading to higher pressure drops, causing more challenges at low fluid velocities.

	Randomly packed bed	Open-cell foam	Periodic open cellular structures	Honeycomb
State	state-of-the-art	development	research	state-of-the-art
Flow pattern	crossmixed	crossmixed	crossmixed	no crossmixing
Radial transport				
- mass	high	high	high	none
- heat	low	high	high	high
Pressure drop	high	low	low	low
Morphology	irregular	irregular	regular	regular
Design freedom	barely	barely	high	barely

Figure 6. Comparison of internals for packed bed reactors [13]

All supports exhibit high radial heat transfer, enhanced by the conductive properties of the metal catalyst supports. As mentioned earlier, radial heat transfer in ceramic honeycomb monoliths is almost zero. Numerous studies have been conducted on open-cell foam supports, which offer advantages in terms of physical properties (e.g., void fraction), thermodynamics (e.g., heat transfer), and mechanical strength. However, these studies often use generalized geometric dimensions, affecting their accuracy. POCS (Periodic Open Cellular Structures) have repeating structures that simplify these studies and allow for reuse in other POCS. By using a unit cell and making slight geometric variations (e.g., stretching or bending), multiple structures can be developed, offering significant design flexibility [9]. Although it depends on the specific design, POCS structures seem to address most of the shortcomings found in other metallic supports.

4 Heat Transfer Models

Understanding the heat transfer properties of these metal supports is crucial, as they depend not only on the solid material but also on solid-fluid interactions. Various heat transfer models have been used and adapted to study thermal behaviour of fixed bed reactors. There are numerous CFD simulations and experimental studies to understand the heat transfer in fixed bed reactors. Based on the simulation results or experimental data, they develop and optimize models to better understand and improve the heat transfer characteristics. Given the presence of the catalyst, a heterogeneous model is required to account for interactions between the catalyst particles and reactants. These two phases have distinct thermal and physical properties, and their interactions need to be accurately modelled to understand the heat transfer processes. However, the complexity of reaction kinetics, the geometry of the supports affecting fluid flow, and numerous unknown parameters make this approach difficult and intricate to solve.

Alternatively, a "pseudo-homogeneous" model can be applied. In this kind of model, the solid phase, which consists of the catalyst particles, and the fluid phase, which consists of the reactants, are considered as one homogeneous continuous phase with superimposed properties, i.e., effective properties that represent both the solid and the fluid phases especially effective thermal conductivities. Another assumption in this model is the uniform temperature distribution. At the steady state the difference between the temperatures of the solid and the fluid can be assumed to be non-existent. The two-dimensional heat transfer equation for a cylindrical reactor is given below:

$$\Lambda_r \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} \right) + \Lambda_{ax} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \right) = u_0 \rho_f c_{p_f} \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + Q \quad (4)$$

where,

Λ_r and Λ_{ax} are effective thermal conductivities in radial and axial direction respectively.

r is the radial distance

z is the axial length

u_0 is the superficial velocity in the reactor

ρ_f is the density of the fluid

c_{p_f} is the heat capacity at constant pressure

Q is the heat generated or consumed by the reaction per unit volume

Based on the variation in radial thermal conductivity, there are two different models available: $\Lambda_r(r)$ -model in which the radial thermal conductivity

depends on the change in porosity in the radial direction or the αW -model where the radial thermal conductivity is assumed to be constant. But there is an additional boundary condition in the latter, which describes the heat transfer at the walls of the reactor.

$$r = R_T: -\Lambda_r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = \alpha_w (T - T_w) \quad (5)$$

Now, the effective radial thermal conductivity is calculated as the sum of stagnant thermal conductivity, radiative heat transfer and thermal dispersion:

$$\Lambda_r = \Lambda_0 + \Lambda_{rad} + \Lambda_d \quad (6)$$

5 Performance of Catalyst Structures in Heat Transfer

5.1 Effect of Material

The influence of lattice structure material has been briefly addressed in Chapter 3. To emphasize, utilizing metals or other conductive materials as catalyst supports, as opposed to non-conductive materials like ceramics, enhances overall heat transfer within the reactor.

Steel-based metallic structures with high thermal conductivity and high design temperature have been extensively studied as bulk materials for open-cell foams and periodic cell structures [24][25]. Numerous researchers have compared various materials, including Ni, FeCrAl, Cu, and CuZn alloys, investigating heat transfer variations among these materials [26]. Their studies emphasize the importance of the bulk material in lattice structures and effective thermal management in compact reactors. In Fischer-Tropsch processes, materials based on aluminium and copper are widely favoured due to their high thermal conductivity. However, selecting the appropriate material for a specific application necessitates considering the operating temperature range [27]. For low-temperature Fischer-Tropsch processes, aluminium serves as an excellent conductor, whereas, for methane reforming, with operating temperatures around 800°C, copper remains the only viable option. Utilising a conductive material can provide better thermal management by preventing thermal runaway, especially in processes such as methanol production where both endothermic and exothermic reactions are taking place [20].

Different materials have been studied including a thermoplastic polymer called ABS which has poor conduction properties, Inconel (IN718) and Titanium alloy (Ti6Al4V) to understand the effect on heat transfer [13]. Stagnant thermal conductivity, which refers to the heat transfer through a medium without fluid movement, has been measured for these materials. Inconel exhibits highest stagnant thermal conductivity of 11.4 W m⁻¹K⁻¹, Titanium alloy has 6.7 W m⁻¹K⁻¹ and ABS has 0.13 W m⁻¹K⁻¹.

The following graph (Fig. 7.) compares the radial thermal conductivity of all three materials with the same lattice design, showing the variation with respect to the superficial mass velocity G . Effective thermal conductivity as mentioned in equation (6), accounts for both the conductive and convective heat transfer mechanisms within the reactor, is used for this comparison. It is evident from the graph that materials with higher thermal conductivity contribute to a more substantial increase in effective thermal conductivity as the mass velocity increases. This highlights the importance of selecting appropriate materials for catalyst supports to optimize heat transfer performance in fixed bed reactors.

Figure 7. Radial effective conductivity of a cubic cell with 7 CPI as a function of Superficial mass velocity [13]

5.2 Effect of Morphology

In cellular structures, the flow pattern is intricate, leading to a convoluted path for heat flux, which in turn impacts the effective thermal conductivity of the material. As a result, different types of unit cells such as cubic, Kelvin and diamond cells with the same stagnant thermal conductivity showcase different heat transfer behaviour thanks to the different tortuosity and flow path of these cells. Busse and Ambrosetti separately studied the heat transfer phenomena in cubic cells in coated and packed composition respectively [13], [28]. However, later on in one research by Littwin, the performance of diamond lattice structures was studied which at similar porosity and hence, the same stagnant thermal conductivity, proved to provide higher heat transfer coefficient [29].

The effect of cell size was examined for various lattices with different CPI values, using the same titanium alloy as the solid material, to understand the impact on thermal conductivity while maintaining consistent solid properties [13]. It was found that there isn't a direct relationship between cell size and the effective thermal conductivity of the lattice, except that larger cell sizes exhibit a steeper slope. This occurs because larger cells enhance the pathways for heat flow, increasing the rate at which thermal conductivity changes with porosity. However, it is important to note that thermal conductivity is primarily influenced by total porosity, which is determined by both the solid material and the lattice structure. The effect of total porosity can be directly correlated with heat conduction: lower porosity results in a denser cellular structure, leading to better conduction within the system. This effect also extends to wall contact, where denser material tightly packed against the

reactor wall exhibits higher conductive effects compared to structures with lower porosity.

The calculation for thermal conductivity for such structures is highly complex, nevertheless, there are many empirical correlations derived earlier to calculate the thermal conductivity in such cases. A parallel can be drawn with the Lemlich correlation for electrical conductivity in high porosity foams due to the similarities in both electrical and thermal conductivity [30]. This correlation states that the ratio of effective stagnant thermal conductivity to solid thermal conductivity is one third of the solid density. It was found that Lemlich model is effective for concave struts when calculating thermal conductivity for cubic and tetrakaidekahedral (Kelvin cell) unit cells[21]. However, for ideal cylindrical struts, a new correlation was developed that results in higher thermal conductivity compared to the Lemlich model. The Fig 8. shows the variation of effective thermal conductivity with the solid fraction. The conductivity increases with increasing volume fraction of the lattice. Bianchi goes on to illustrate the influence of the strut shape in cubic and Kelvin cells on the conductivity.

Figure 8. Dimensionless effective conductivity of Kelvin & cubic cell vs solid fraction [21]

Braconi studied the heat transfer in open-cell foams and investigated the influence of geometric properties such as cell size, porosity and the ratio of the node to strut diameter [31]. The influence of node to the strut diameter was found to be quite strong on the effective thermal conductivity. When the node to strut diameter ratio is small or lower the heat transfer is more effective. This can be explained due to cross-sectional area of the strut. So, the thicker the strut, the higher the conductive heat transfer through it. When

the node to strut diameter ratio is higher, indicating the small diameter of the strut, heat transfer is strongly affected. In POCS structures, the ratio of node and the strut diameter can be more closely controlled and when the ratio is maintained close to one, the effective heat conductivity can be increased by almost 30%.

Contrary to the effects of cell type and cell size mentioned earlier, in a research study for foams with uniform struts by, no effects due to the type of unit cell and cell size were found [31]. However, the effects were noted in case of non-uniform strut sizes. In another study by Littwin over diamond lattices, it was highlighted that the thermal dispersion is highly influenced by the strut diameter. The larger strut diameter tends to improve the thermal dispersion due to increase in convolution of the flow path [29].

5.3 Effect of wall coupling

Wall coupling is a critical concept in heat transfer studies and refers to the contact between the reactor wall and the lattice structure. Ideally, the lattice structure should fit snugly inside the reactor to ensure efficient conductive heat transfer between the lattice and the wall. If there is too much gap or dead space between them, conductive heat transfer will be reduced. Conversely, if the lattice structure is too large, it may get damaged or bent during assembly. Different material of the lattice structure and the reactor can also affect the wall coupling when operating in higher temperature range due to differential thermal expansion of these materials [9].

Many studies have overlooked the heat transfer between the wall and the lattice structure, focusing solely on the lattice. However, improper wall coupling can lead to increased heat transfer resistance, making it an important factor that cannot be ignored. In a study by Busse, a stagnant and a dynamic part were considered to understand the effects of wall coupling [13]. The stagnant part refers to the conduction between the wall and the cellular structure, while the dynamic part involves convective heat transfer. Convective heat transfer is influenced by the fluid properties; if the fluid has low conductivity, dynamic heat transport will be adversely affected [21], [32]. This was experimentally proven by Boger and Heibel where they studied the wall coupling effect in honeycomb monoliths [33].

Another experiment conducted on cubic cell POCS structure was done reducing the contact slowly by cutting the outer wire structure from 100% connection to only 12.5% [13]. This reduction led to a 35% decrease in heat transfer, and when the remaining 12.5% contact was also removed, heat transfer ceased entirely.

5.4 Comparison of heat transfer in randomly packed beds and structured packed beds

A study performed by Fratalocchi in 2020, investigated the reactions in fixed-bed Fischer-Tropsch process reactor with POCS structures which were packed with Co/Pt/Al₂O₃ catalyst pellets [9]. The same experiments were performed with packed foams and randomly packed bed as well for comparison. Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the temperature profile differences among packed bed, packed foam, and packed POCS structures.

Figure 9. Comparison of temperature difference in the radial direction with the reaction heat per unit volume [9].

The graph in Figure 9 depicts the temperature variations in the radial direction for these three packed structures. In the experiment with randomly packed bed, thermal runaway was experienced. Consequently, the slope is steepest for the packed bed, indicating a significant temperature difference. Packed foams exhibit a lower slope than packed beds but higher than packed POCS [9], [20]. This lower slope in packed POCS suggests that the structured conductive linkage within the solid material greatly enhances internal heat transfer, resulting in a more uniform temperature distribution.

Figure 10 presents a graph comparing the temperature profiles for packed bed, packed foams, and packed POCS structures. The slope in the graph represents the overall heat transfer coefficient, including the wall heat resistance. Similar to the radial temperature profiles, packed POCS outperforms both packed bed and packed foams. According to Fratalocchi, the

improved overall heat transfer is due in part to better internal conductive heat transfer, but largely to reduced wall resistance and better contact between the lattice and the wall.

Figure 10. Comparison of external temperature difference with the reaction heat per unit volume [9]

6 Methodology

In this thesis, the aim is to optimize the design of intensified catalytic reactors by investigating the impact of different metallic structures in the packed bed reactor on heat transfer. The experiments were specifically designed to examine how flow patterns, tortuosity, and turbulence, as influenced by various lattice structures, affect heat transfer performance. The heat transfer experiments were conducted in a non-reactive environment at atmospheric pressure.

6.1 Metallic structures

Several metallic structure samples of dimensions 30.04 mm O.D. x 70 mm length, with different unit cell types including honeycomb monolith, cubic, diamond and TPMS structures were fabricated for the heat transfer experiments. For TPMS lattices four samples were designed such as diamond network, diamond matrix with two different cell sizes and gyroid matrix and Matlab with Flatpack add-on was used for it; all other samples were designed with the help of Oqton 3DXpert CAD software. In all the samples, the strut or wall diameter was kept constant at 0.35 mm during the design phase. This choice was made to align the minimum feature size with the current manufacturing constraints of metal Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) technology. Each sample is provided with three cylindrical cavities with 2 mm diameter for thermocouples in order to measure the temperature at three radial positions i.e. 0 mm, 5 mm and 10 mm from the centre.

Figure 11. Samples (a) Diamond cell (b) Diamond cell with outer wall (c) Diamond Matrix & (d) Gyroid Matrix

To investigate the effect of cell size, diamond cell lattices were fabricated in three sizes: 2.8 mm, 3.4 mm, and 4.6 mm with a total of 3 samples with 2.8 mm cell size without outer wall. An additional diamond lattice sample was produced with an outer wall and a cell size of 2.8 mm. apart from the diamond cell lattices, one monolith and a cubic cell lattice with 4 mm cell size

was manufactured. Four distinct TPMS (Triply Periodic Minimal Surface) structures were created, including one diamond network (also referred to as a diamond skeleton) and two diamond matrix lattices (also referred to as diamond sheets) with varying cell sizes. A gyroid matrix-type TPMS lattice was also fabricated to allow comparison with the diamond matrix lattice. Figure 11 presents the images of various samples generated for the experiments.

Geometrical properties of the samples are summarized in the table 1. The designed samples were manufactured from EOS AlSi10Mg aluminium alloy and 3D printed using L-PBF in EOS M290 printer and heat treated to enhance the mechanical properties of the lattices. The outer diameter of all the samples matched the inner diameter of the reactor body, therefore, the samples were manually machined to fit tightly within the reactor.

Table 1: Design Parameters for the lattice samples

S.N.	Sample	Cell Size, mm	Porosity	Outer Wall thickness, mm
1	Honeycomb Monolith	4.4	0.78	-
2	Diamond cell with outer wall	2.8	0.93	0.5
3	Diamond cell	2.8	0.93	-
4	Diamond cell	3.4	0.951	-
5	Diamond cell	4.6	0.973	-
6	Cubic cell	4.0	0.964	-
7	Diamond Network	2.6	0.86	-
8	Diamond Matrix	3.9	0.7	-
9	Diamond Matrix	5.6	0.78	-
10	Gyroid Matrix	3.9	0.74	-

The actual strut diameter was measured through microscopic imaging to cater for the differences in the designs and the end product. To study the heat transfer for a simple packed bed, the honeycomb monolith sample was cut to keep the thermocouple cavities.

6.2 Experiment Setup

An existing fixed bed reactor was modified to accommodate for the heat transfer experiments. The reactor, as shown in Figure 12 & 13, was 3D printed

and made of SS316L material designed for temperatures up to 350 °C and pressure of 30 bar.

Figure 12. Heat transfer reactor schematic diagram

It consisted of a tubular core of I.D. 30.04 mm where the lattice structures are inserted, and oil channels around the core for heating/cooling. The reactor wall thickness is 2 mm, and the total length of the reactor is 75 mm; however, the heating/cooling is provided only for the middle section of the reactor body of about 60 mm. There are total of 12 oil channels with an I.D. of 2.5 mm each spread around the reactor in zig-zag fashion. The length of each channel is approximately 1.3 times more than 60 mm. The reactor has been provided with an inlet (at the bottom) and outlet (at the top) nozzles for the oil circulation through the channels.

Figure 13. Heat transfer reactor setup

Lauda P2E oil thermostat was used to heat Dibenzyl toluene oil (Lauda Ultra 350) to the desired temperature and circulate it through the reactor [34], [35]. The oil temperature is monitored at both the inlet and outlet points of the reactor to ensure consistent heating. To achieve accurate flow control, the oil flow rate was calibrated across different thermostat stages and temperatures. During the calibration process, oil was circulated through the reactor's oil side, though it was not operated in a closed-loop system. This approach may have impacted discharge pressure levels and introduced slight variations in mass flow measurements. Furthermore, the maximum temperature for calibration was capped at 120 °C, as temperatures above this level led to oil vaporization, which posed a safety risk in an open environment. To calculate oil flow rates for the experiments, mass flow at each temperature was converted to volumetric flow rate using the density at respective temperature, and a polynomial equation was developed through curve fitting. To avoid any heat losses, the oil pipes from the oil thermostat to the reactor with thermal insulation are used which are connected with the reactor body through threaded connectors.

Standard PN40 flanges and Klinger MLX graphite gaskets are used on both ends of the reactor to ensure tight sealing and prevent any gas leakage. The top flange is provided with a nozzle for gas flow in the reactor and inlet for 3 thermocouples to keep them stable and in the correct position during the experiments. The flanges have been modified to provide longer entry length and as a result, higher volume to facilitate even gas distribution and settling before it enters the reactor. 1.5 mm K-type single point thermocouples have been used for temperature measurement. All thermocouples were calibrated before and in between the experiments to avoid flawed measurement. For calibration, an electric calibrator oven was used, and the thermocouples were tested between the range of 40-200 °C. Air is supplied at atmospheric pressure and temperature of 23 to 25 °C with the help of a mass flow controller. Bronkhorst F-202AV thermal mass flow controller was used to control the gas flow rate, using Bronkhorst Flow DDE software. The mass flow controller was calibrated for air before conducting the experiments where the air was flowed through the empty reactor setup and the flowrate was measured using a calibrated flow meter. This mass flow controller allows a flow rate ranging from 15 to 65 ndm³/min, corresponding to a valve opening between 20% and 80%.

6.3 Experiments

The reactor setup process begins by placing a lattice structure at the centre of the reactor chamber, with a fine mesh positioned at the bottom to securely hold the packing material. Silicon Carbide (SiC) particles, with a size of 210 µm, are then packed into the reactor, ensuring a tight and uniform distribution. Thermocouples are carefully inserted into the lattice structure thermocouple cavities, extending down to the base of the lattice to enable precise temperature measurements. After placement, the reactor flanges are secured with M8 rods to ensure a firm seal.

Next, the air hose and oil pipes are connected to the reactor, and all manual valves are opened as indicated in the P&ID diagram as shown in Figure 14. With connections checked, an initial airflow is started to test for any leaks at connection points. The thermostat is then switched on, initiating oil circulation through the reactor in a closed loop. The reactor wall temperature is gradually increased to 150 °C to minimize thermal stress and prevent damage to the oil pump. Insulating material is wrapped around the setup to reduce heat loss, and approximately two hours are required to reach the target temperature.

During experiments, temperature measurements are taken at seven distinct axial positions along each radial position within the reactor. To achieve this, thermocouples are manually incrementally raised by 1 cm for each measurement. For consistency across experiments, small markings are made on each thermocouple, beginning from the lowest point i.e. 70 mm within the

lattice structure and extending upwards in 1 cm intervals to the seventh position i.e. 10 mm. The top reading at 0 mm is not used for the calculations as the oil heating is provided in the middle section of the reactor and the top of the inserts would remain outside the heating zone.

Figure 14. P&ID diagram of the experiment setup

In the experiments, the wall temperature was maintained at 150 °C, while the airflow varied between 0.484 ndm³/s and 0.829 ndm³/s. Once both the wall temperature and airflow stabilized, the temperatures at each of the three thermocouples were recorded. Starting with measurements at the bottom of the lattice (70 mm), the thermocouples were then raised by 1 cm. After achieving a new steady state at each position, the temperatures were logged again.

Two approaches were tested for temperature measurement. In the first method, the airflow was kept constant, and temperatures were recorded sequentially as the thermocouples were raised through each axial position. After completing measurements at one airflow, the thermocouples were returned to the bottom of the lattice for measurements at a new flow rate. In the second method, temperature measurements were taken at each axial position for all airflow rates before adjusting the thermocouples to the next axial position. The second approach proved to be more accurate, as it ensured identical thermocouple positions for each airflow rate. It was noticed that it took longer for the temperature to stabilize after changing the airflow rate which means that the second approach overall took longer time for each lattice. After the experiments, the setup was slowly cooled down before unpacking the reactor setup which took about 3 hours.

6.4 Calculations

In this study, several key assumptions were made to simplify the heat transfer calculations and ensure clarity in data interpretation. During the experiments the inlet and outlet temperature on the oil side was measured and the temperature difference was noted to be 1.5-2 °C. Given the small difference, it was assumed negligible, allowing us to treat the oil as an isothermal heat source or sink and to focus on temperature changes occurring within the air phase only. It is assumed that there is no heat transfer resistance on the oil side due to the use of consistent oil flow rates, calibrated circulation through the reactor, and thermal insulation around the oil pipes. In addition, the threaded connections and use of high-quality sealing components ensured minimal thermal losses. Additionally, it was assumed that the air entering the reactor was uniformly distributed across the entire packed bed, thus creating a homogenous temperature and flow profile throughout the reactor. This uniformity in air distribution simplified the calculations by reducing the likelihood of localized hot or cold spots within the reactor, thereby ensuring more consistent heat transfer rates across the entire bed. Furthermore, it was assumed that there was no pressure drop in the setup, and the experiments were conducted at atmospheric pressure, further simplifying the analysis.

All the thermal properties for the material involved are presented in Table 2. Air properties for each case were calculated based on the average bulk mean temperature.

Table 2: Thermal properties

Properties	Unit	Dibenzyl toluene	SS 316L	AlSi10Mg	SiC particles
Density	kg/m ³	954	8000	2670	1487
Thermal Conductivity	W/m K	0.114	15	160	120
Kinematic Viscosity	m ² /s	0.0000015			
Dynamic Viscosity	kg/ms	0.001431			
Heat Capacity	J/kgK	2030			

6.4.1 Heat Transfer Calculations

A one-dimensional steady state heat transfer model was adopted for calculating the heat transfer coefficient which assumes that the fluid exhibits ideal plug flow behaviour. The equations involved are shown below:

$$\rho_{gas} u c_p \frac{dT_c}{dz} = \frac{4}{d_t} U_{overall} (T_{oil} - T_c) \quad (7)$$

Equation 7 presents the 1-D steady state heat transfer for a fluid flowing through a heated/cooled pipe. The bulk mean temperature for each axial position is calculated as in Equation 8 using the radial temperature curve assuming constant heat capacity which is derived by curve fitting for a polynomial equation in Equation 9.

$$T_c = \frac{2 \int_0^{r_t} T(r) r dr}{r_t^2} \quad (8)$$

$$T(r) = ar^2 + br + c \quad (9)$$

The analytical solution for equation 7 is provided in equation 10 where gas properties at bulk mean temperatures have been used. Linear regression of the analytical solution provides the overall heat transfer coefficient for each case, and heat transfer coefficient on the structure side is calculated using eq. 12.

$$T_c(z) = T_{oil} - (T_{oil} - T_{c,z=0}) \exp\left(-\frac{4U_{overall}z}{\rho u c_p d_t}\right) \quad (10)$$

The heat transfer coefficient on the oil side was determined using an oil flow rate of 2.227 L/min. Given that the Reynolds number was found to be below 2300, the Sieder-Tate equation (as shown in Eq. (13)) was applied to calculate the Nusselt number where the temperature at the walls and in the bulk of the oil channels was assumed to be equal, allowing for the subsequent calculation of U_{oil} .

$$\frac{1}{U_{overall}} = \frac{1}{U_{air}} + \frac{1}{U_{oil}} + \frac{d_{wall}}{k_{wall}} \quad (11)$$

$$U_{air} = \left(\frac{1}{U_{overall}} - \frac{1}{U_{oil}} - \frac{d_{wall}}{k_{wall}} \right)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

$$Nu = 1.86 Re^{\frac{1}{3}} Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{D}{L} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (13)$$

6.4.2 Porosity Calculations

The packing efficiency is measured using equation 14 which indicates the ratio of volume occupied by the SiC particles to the volume remaining after the volume occupied by the metallic inserts. The total volume was calculated using the volume for cylinder with dimensions of the metallic structure. For calculating the volume of the particles, firstly bulk density of the particles was

measured using a measuring cylinder and weighing the particles present in the specified volume. This was done for multiple volumes and the average density mentioned in Table 2 was used for the calculation. On the other hand, the weight of the metallic structures was measured, and its density was used to get the volume occupied by the inserts. Here, the assumption is that the internal porosity of the AlSi10Mg structures was assumed to be zero i.e. they are 100% dense.

These calculations provide complementary insights into the porosity characteristics of the packing, with results summarized and compared in Table 2. This analysis provides a comparison in a direct volumetric evaluation alongside a simplified geometric approach, helping to capture a broader understanding of the packing properties in various cell structures.

$$1 - \varepsilon_{packing} = \frac{V_{particles}}{V_{total} - V_{structure}} = \frac{V_{particles}}{\varepsilon_{structure} V_{total}} \quad (14)$$

$$\varepsilon_{structure} = \frac{(V_{total} - V_{structure})}{V_{total}} \quad (15)$$

$$\varepsilon_{total} = \frac{V_{void}}{V_{total}} = \varepsilon_{structure} \varepsilon_{packing} \quad (16)$$

6.4.3 Mathematical Model

Equations 17 & 18 outline the calculation methods for determining the window diameter of the cubic cell and diamond cell configurations, respectively. Equation 19 has been employed for calculating the porosity of the packing which relies on the particle diameter and the window diameter of the lattice, specifically addressing the porosity associated with the structured packed bed arrangement [36].

$$d_{window} = d_{cell} - d_s \quad (17)$$

$$d_{window} = \left(\frac{6\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{d_{cell}\sqrt{2}}{4} - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{3} d_s \right) \quad (18)$$

$$\varepsilon_{packing} = 0.375 + 0.0018 \left(\frac{d_{particle}}{d_{window}} \right) + 0.607 \left(\frac{d_{particle}}{d_{window}} \right)^2 \quad (19)$$

To simplify and enhance the accuracy of heat transfer modelling in fixed bed reactors, a heat transfer model was developed using a thermal circuit,

highlighted in Figure 15, that incorporates a two-phase system: the POCS structure as the solid network and the combination of catalyst particles and fluid creating a pseudo-homogeneous phase [36], [37]. This model can be applied for non-reactive steady state heat transfer experiments under heating or cooling conditions and therefore this heat transfer model has been employed to compute the air-side heat transfer coefficient across all diamond cell lattice structures.

Figure 15. Schematic of heat transfer pathways in POCS structures [28]

Within the reactor, each interaction involving heat flux is evaluated through specific thermal resistances. At the wall, the first part of the thermal circuit includes two resistances connected in parallel: one due to the effective gap between the structure and the wall, represented by $h_{w,structure}$, and the other from the wall heat transfer of the packed particles, represented by $h_{w,packed}$.

To determine the thermal resistance at the wall, the heat transfer coefficient is calculated specifically for the packing and the POCS, following equations 20-24. In this model, a fixed Nusselt number of 4.51 has been utilized in the equation 20 [36][38].

$$h_{w,structure} = \frac{Nu_{static} k_{gas}}{d_{cell}} \quad (20)$$

$$h_{w,packing}^{static} = \left(\frac{k_{gas}}{d_{particle}} \right) \left(2\varepsilon_{packing} + \frac{1-\varepsilon_{packing}}{0.0024} \left(\frac{d_t}{d_{particle}} \right)^{-1.58} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{k_{gas}}{k_{particle}} \right) \quad (21)$$

$$Re_p < 1200 \quad h_{w,packing}^{convective} = 0.0835 \left(\frac{k_{gas}}{d_{particle}} \right) Re_p^{0.91} \quad (22)$$

$$Re_p > 1200 \quad h_{w,packing}^{convective} = 1.23 \left(\frac{k_{gas}}{d_{particle}} \right) Re_p^{0.51} \quad (23)$$

$$R_{wall} = \frac{1}{h_{w,POCS} + h_{w,packingstatic} + h_{w,packingconvective}} \quad (24)$$

The thermal circuit model also incorporates the internal resistance contributions from the lattice itself, the packed bed, and the interface connecting the lattice and the packing. Moving from the near-wall region to the core of the bed, heat flux can follow two main paths. One path involves a convective mechanism through the gas/packed particle pseudo-homogeneous phase, represented by $k_{eff,packed}$ and the other path involves conduction through the connected solid framework of the structure, represented by $k_{eff,structure}$. The effective thermal conductivity of the solid structure is primarily determined by heat conduction within the structure design and remains unaffected by the packing. As a result, only the solid structure porosity is factored into the calculations in equation 25 [39].

$$k_{eff,structure} = k_{solid,structure} [0.36 + 0.64(1 - \varepsilon_{structure})] (1 - \varepsilon_{structure}) \quad (25)$$

$$k_{eff,packingstatic} = (1 - \varepsilon_{structure}) \left(k_{gas} \varepsilon_{packing} + \frac{k_{gas}(1 - \varepsilon_{packing})}{0.22\varepsilon_{packing}^2 + \frac{2}{3} \frac{k_{gas}}{k_{particle}}} \right) \quad (26)$$

$$k_{eff,packingconvective} = k_{gas} \left(\frac{Re_p Pr}{Pe_{rif}} \right) \quad (27)$$

$$Pe_{rif} = 8.65 \left[1 + 19.4 * \left(\frac{d_{particle}}{d_t} \right)^2 \right] \quad (28)$$

Additionally, an extra resistance must be considered for the heat transfer between the solid structure and the pseudo-homogeneous phase, represented by $U_{structure \rightarrow Packing}$ in equation 30. This resistance is in series with the resistance of the metallic structure itself. To calculate the heat transfer between the lattice structure and the packing equations 21-23 have been applied. In these calculations, the cell diameter is used in place of the tube diameter, allowing for a more accurate representation of the heat exchange characteristics specific to the diamond cell lattice and its unique geometry. This approach allows for a comprehensive assessment of the thermal interactions between the lattice and the surrounding packing material. The specific surface area for the diamond cell lattice is calculated using the equation 29 [40].

$$S_{v,structure} = 4\pi d_s^2 / d_{cell}^3 \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}d_{cell}}{d_s} + 2\sqrt{3} - 3 - 2\sqrt{2} \right) \quad (29)$$

$$R_{IF} = \frac{4}{d_t S_{v,structure} U_{structure \rightarrow Packing}} \quad (30)$$

Equation 33 represents the total internal resistance calculated by arranging internal resistance of the packed bed (equation 31) in parallel with the resistance from the structure, given in equation 32.

$$R_p = \frac{d_t}{6.13(k_{eff,packingstatic} + k_{eff,packingconvective})} \quad (31)$$

$$R_{structure} = \frac{d_t}{6.13(k_{eff,structure})} \quad (32)$$

$$R_{INT} = \frac{R_p(R_{structure} + R_{IF})}{R_p + (R_{structure} + R_{IF})} \quad (33)$$

The heat transfer coefficient on the air side is calculated using equation 34.

$$U_{air,th} = (R_{wall} + R_{INT})^{-1} \quad (34)$$

7 Results

7.1 Porosity Calculations

Table 3 presents the porosity values calculated for the designed lattice structures. The porosity of the structures ($\epsilon_{structure}$) was determined by dividing the volume of the sample by the total volume of the reactor cavity. When comparing the porosity of the structures with the theoretical porosities presented in Table 1, the structure porosity after manufacturing is lower than the theoretical porosities. This is due to the limitations or differences in end product after fabrication and design phase. This discrepancy arises from limitations or variations between the design phase and the final product after fabrication. The packing efficiency in Table 3 demonstrates how each sample is filled with SiC particles. Samples with smaller cell sizes exhibit lower packing efficiency, as explained by equation 19, while packing efficiency increases as the cell sizes increase.

Table 3: Calculated packing efficiency for the fabricated lattice samples

S.N.	Sample	Cell Size (mm)	$\epsilon_{structure}$	$1 - \epsilon_{packing}$
1	Monolith	4.35	0.774	0.893
2.1	Diamond cell	2.8	0.854	0.718
2.2	Diamond cell	2.8	0.849	0.711
2.3	Diamond cell	2.8	0.844	0.717
3	Diamond cell	3.4	0.887	0.813
4	Diamond cell	4.6	0.929	0.859
5	Diamond cell (wall)	2.8	0.792	0.680
6	Cubic cell	4.0	0.911	0.822
7	Diamond Network	3.0	0.787	0.695
8	Diamond Matrix	4.3	0.576	0.824
9	Diamond Matrix	6.0	0.671	0.926
10	Gyroid Matrix	4.3	0.628	0.679

Table 4 shows the actual strut diameters measured in the fabricated lattice structures, which have slightly grown from the intended 0.35 mm—close to the 3D printing manufacturing limit—to about 0.45 mm after fabrication. Specific surface areas for the diamond cell structures were calculated using equation 29, while for TPMS lattices, the values were obtained via the Flatpack software. The lattice structures were subsequently redesigned to maintain the same overall characteristics, with only the strut diameter adjusted to 0.45 mm, allowing for a comparative analysis of surface area to volume ratios. Interestingly, Table 4., highlights a notable difference in specific surface areas between diamond cell lattices and other TPMS structures, underscoring the distinct structural properties of diamond cells in terms of surface area efficiency. Hydraulic diameter is calculated due to the irregularity in the geometry of the samples as shown below

$$d_H = \frac{4\varepsilon}{S_v}$$

Table 4: Geometric properties of fabricated lattice samples

S.N.	Sample	Cell Size (mm)	Specific surface area (1/m)	Hydraulic diameter (m)
1	Monolith	4.35	-	-
2	Diamond cell	2.8	975.226	0.00361
3	Diamond cell	2.8	694.201	0.00528
4	Diamond cell	3.4	401.067	0.00950
5	Diamond cell (wall)	4.6	975.226	0.00361
6	Cubic cell	4.0	-	-
7	Diamond Network	3.0	1345.6	0.00250
8	Diamond Matrix	4.3	2052.8	0.00134
9	Diamond Matrix	6.0	1435.1	0.00215
10	Gyroid Matrix	4.3	1717.2	0.00168

7.2 Temperature Profiles

Figure 16 presents a comparison of the temperature profiles for the 2.8 mm diamond cell lattice with an outer wall, across four different airflow rates at each radial position. The axial positions, ranging from 10 mm to 70 mm, represent temperature measurements from the top to the bottom of the lattice. The mass velocities corresponding to each curve are also indicated on the graph. The profiles for radial position 5 mm and 10 mm are present in the Appendix Figure B1.

As shown, temperature gradually increases along the axial length from the top, where cool air enters the reactor, to the bottom, where it has absorbed heat from the reactor walls. As shown in Figure 16, the temperatures are lower at higher air flow rates due to shorter residence time in the reactor. Conversely, the temperature is highest at the lowest mass velocity, indicating reduced cooling effect at lower flows.

It is worth noting that at any given axial position, temperatures are consistently lowest at the centre of the lattice (0 mm) and highest near the wall (10 mm), highlighting the radial temperature gradient influenced by proximity to the heated reactor walls.

Figure 16. Temperature profiles for 2.8 mm diamond cell lattice with outer wall at radial position 0 mm

Examining the graphs in Figure 17, we observe a temperature profile for diamond cell lattice of cell size 2.8 mm at a mass velocity of 1.303 kg/m²s. Temperature profiles for cell sizes 3.4 mm and 4.6 mm are present in Appendix Figure B.2. Although the overall shapes of the curves for each lattice

appear similar, the 2.8 mm cell size lattice shows temperature curves for each radial position that are closely aligned, indicating smaller temperature differences across the radial direction.

As cell size increases, however, the radial temperature differences also increase. This effect can likely be attributed to improved thermal conduction in smaller cell sizes, resulting in lower porosity in the lattice structure, which allows for more uniform temperature distribution. Additionally, the temperature at the bottom of the lattice is notably higher for smaller cell sizes, further emphasizing the influence of cell size on temperature uniformity and thermal conduction throughout the lattice.

This suggests that smaller cell sizes provide better heat conduction within the lattice, resulting in a more consistent temperature profile across both radial and axial positions compared to larger cell sizes.

Figure 17. Temperature profile at $G=1.303 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$ for diamond cell lattice with cell size of 2.8 mm

7.3 Heat Transfer Coefficients

The air-side heat transfer coefficient was calculated using the one-dimensional heat transfer model outlined in the previous chapter. As mentioned earlier, all the samples were machined to fit inside the reactor body and these samples were then qualitatively classified into three fit levels to assess the impact of wall contact on heat transfer:

1. High fit, indicating a very tight fit with excellent wall contact;

2. Medium fit, with good contact in some regions but not all; and
3. Low fit, where the lattice was loosely fit, resulting in poor wall contact.

Table 5. displays the heat transfer coefficient at $G=1.303 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$ for three identical samples, each with a cell size of 2.8 mm, with a different fit level along with a comparison to a lattice with an integrated outer wall, which provided exceptionally good wall contact. The results clearly indicate that heat transfer is highly sensitive to wall contact quality: the heat transfer coefficient for the low fit sample was even lower than that of the monolith as displayed in Figure 18. Furthermore, there is a noticeable improvement in heat transfer between the low and medium fits, but the difference diminishes at higher fit levels, suggesting that after a certain threshold of wall contact, further improvements have less impact. The heat transfer coefficient of diamond cell sample with lowest fitting is approximately 44% lower than that for the sample with an outer wall while the drop in the heat transfer coefficient for the sample with medium fit is around 11%. As a result, all the samples with low fit, indicating poor wall contact were excluded from the result analysis.

Table 5: Comparison of heat transfer coefficients for diamond cell samples with 2.8 mm cell size with respect to fitting

Sample	POCS	Fitting	U_{air} (W/m ² K)
2.1	Diamond cell	Low	128.223
2.2	Diamond cell	Medium	202.693
2.3	Diamond cell	High	216.561
5	Diamond cell (wall)	High	229.052

To further understand the separate effects of lattice structure and particle packing on heat transfer, additional experiments were conducted. For packed bed analysis, the monolith structure was modified by cutting it to allow placement of thermocouples, and then packed with SiC particles. The resulting heat transfer coefficient at a mass velocity of $G=1.303 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$, shown by the first bar from the left in Figure 18, was considerably lower than the values obtained with even the diamond lattice structure without particle bed. The error bars representing $\pm 5\%$ in the graphs for the heat transfer coefficient account for the variations observed across repeated experiments, reflecting the consistency of the measurements and potential experimental uncertainties, which are discussed in detail in Chapter 8.

In a second experiment, a diamond lattice with the smallest cell size (2.8 mm) was tested without particle packing (second bar from the left in Figure 18), and the heat transfer coefficient observed was notably higher than that of the packed bed, underscoring the significance of structured lattices in enhancing heat transfer. The monolith structure, characterized by channelled flow for the gas, exhibited a lower heat transfer coefficient than the diamond lattice with a 4.6 mm cell size, even though monolith structure has smaller window diameter.

Figure 18 further demonstrates that the heat transfer coefficient increases with decreasing cell size, which aligns with expectations as smaller cells tend to enhance conductive heat transfer by providing more surface area and thermal pathways.

Figure 18. Air-side heat transfer coefficient for various samples at $G=1.303 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$

Figures 19 & 20 provide a comparison in the heat transfer coefficient at $G=1.303 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$ with the porosity values of these solid structures. Figure 18 shows an inverse relationship between the heat transfer coefficient and porosity. To compare the heat transfer coefficient of cubic cell with diamond cell, a linear curve was fitted to find the value for diamond cell with 4 mm cell size heat transfer coefficient, which came out to be $172.3 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ with $R^2=0.93$ which is better than $161 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ calculated for cubic cell structure. However, since only one cubic cell sample was tested, definitive conclusions cannot be drawn.

Figure 19. Air side heat transfer coefficient compared with structure porosity for diamond cell lattice structures

Figure 20. Air side heat transfer coefficient compared with structure porosity for TPMS structures

A similar trend can be seen in Figure 20, where the TPMS samples are compared. Here, the heat transfer coefficient generally increases as porosity decreases, as seen in both the diamond matrix and gyroid matrix lattices.

Interestingly, although the diamond network has a higher porosity, it still achieves a higher heat transfer coefficient compared to a diamond matrix with a larger cell size. The diamond network and matrix structures exhibit distinct designs, yet further data would be necessary to draw conclusive insights into the influence of structural variations on heat transfer behaviour.

Figure 21 illustrates the relationship between the heat transfer coefficient and mass velocity for TPMS and diamond lattice samples with an outer wall. Across all samples, the heat transfer coefficient consistently increases with flow rate, which is expected due to the enhanced convective heat transfer as airflow through the reactor intensifies. However, each sample exhibits a distinct slope, indicating varying rates of heat transfer response with increasing flow.

Figure 21. Comparison of heat transfer coefficient with mass velocity

Notably, the diamond cell and diamond matrix structures display significantly steeper slopes compared to the diamond network and gyroid matrix, suggesting that these structures have higher sensitivity to changes in flow rate. This variation in slopes can likely be attributed to differences in geometry, tortuosity, and structural complexity within each lattice, which directly affect the flow patterns and thermal pathways through the packed bed of the reactor. The complex geometry of diamond matrix structures may create more turbulence and surface contact, leading to increased convective heat transfer, while the comparatively smoother flow paths of the diamond network and gyroid structures yield a more gradual rise. However, higher turbulence may lead to higher pressure drop in case of diamond matrix

structures. Steeper slope would be more beneficial in dynamic operations and improved heat removal in exothermic conditions. However, it is important to note that the TPMS samples have lower structural porosity (Table 3) indicating that TPMS structures used more material for the printing compared to diamond cell samples. Based on the evaluation, diamond cell structures with small cell size would be an optimum choice in applications for methanol synthesis. Further detailed analysis of the flow dynamics within each structure is required to fully explain these differences.

7.4 Theoretical heat transfer coefficients

Theoretical values for the air-side heat transfer coefficient for the diamond cell lattices were calculated using the equations outlined in Chapter 6.4.3. These theoretical results were then compared to experimental values in a parity plot, shown in Figure 22. Although the theoretical values tend to be higher than the experimental results, the discrepancy is generally within a 30% range, with smaller cell size lattices showing even closer alignment between theoretical and experimental data. This reduction in variation for smaller cell sizes suggests that these structures may provide a better match to theoretical predictions, possibly due to enhanced conductive effects. However, for larger lattice geometries, deviations between theoretical and experimental results suggest the need for refined modelling to account for complex flow and thermal interactions.

Figure 22. Parity plot for heat transfer coefficient

8 Error Estimation

Although the reactor setup was carefully designed to ensure precision in heat transfer experiments, several potential sources of error were identified due to the complexity and sensitivity of the system. The compact and robust design, while advantageous for certain applications, presents inherent challenges, such as limitations in controlling flow uniformity, maintaining consistent temperature gradients, and ensuring precise measurement accuracy. Error estimation, therefore, becomes a critical aspect of experimental analysis, particularly for small-scale setups where system sensitivity and manual intervention can introduce variability.

One significant observation was the impact of flow fluctuations through the mass flow controller, particularly at higher valve openings (e.g., 60% and 70%). To minimize these fluctuations, experiments were conducted at lower valve openings, with a maximum of 50%. However, this adjustment introduced a trade-off: the reduced airflow resulted in smaller temperature differences across radial and axial positions, which may influence the resolution of heat transfer measurements. Another potential source of error was slight variabilities in the oil-side temperature. Trials were conducted by varying the oil temperature in 1°C increments, during which the air-side temperature varied by 0.2–0.3°C at lower flow rates and up to 0.5°C at higher air flow rates. While these changes did not significantly alter the overall temperature profile within the reactor, repeated tests revealed that the air-side heat transfer coefficient was quite sensitive to even minor variations in the temperature profile. Another factor contributing to potential deviations was heat loss from the reactor system. Despite using thermal insulation on the oil pipes and reactor body, some degree of heat dissipation into the surrounding environment was unavoidable. This heat loss could affect the uniformity of the temperature distribution within the reactor and influence the accuracy of the measured heat transfer coefficients. Ensuring minimal heat loss is especially critical in compact setups like this, where even small losses can significantly impact the thermal behaviour of the system. Furthermore, the air-side heat transfer coefficient was strongly influenced by the oil-side heat transfer coefficient, emphasizing the importance of accurate characterization of oil-side conditions. Calculating the oil-side heat transfer coefficient required selecting an appropriate heat transfer equation and determining the flow regime (laminar or turbulent) of the oil flow. However, as the oil flow rate was not directly measured under experimental conditions, this uncertainty may have introduced subtle variations in the air-side heat transfer coefficient values.

Additionally, it was assumed that there was no pressure drop in the setup, and the experiments were conducted at atmospheric pressure. Ignoring the pressure drop may have overlooked certain flow dynamics, such as changes

in velocity and turbulence, which could affect heat transfer efficiency. However, given the experimental conditions, this assumption was deemed reasonable and its impact on the results was considered minimal.

To assess the repeatability of the experiments and estimate error margins, some runs were repeated under identical conditions. The heat transfer coefficients obtained from these trials were used to calculate the average heat transfer coefficient and the percentage error for each measurement using the following equations: The Results chapter should also discuss the reliability of the material used in the study. Theses that are literature studies typically do not have a Results chapter, but instead a Summary section that has conclusions, their evaluation and their significance.

$$h_{average} = \frac{(h_1 + h_2)}{2}$$

$$deviation \% = \frac{h - h_{average}}{h_{average}}$$

The heat transfer coefficient values and their corresponding error percentages are provided in the table below.

S.N.	Sample	Cell size (mm)	Uair (W/m²K) (Experiment 1)	Uair (W/m²K) (Experiment 2)	deviation%
1	Diamond cell	2.8	245.777	263.536	±3.5%
2	Diamond Matrix	4.3	354.829	325.936	±4.3%
3	Gyroid Matrix	4.3	246.684	250.248	±0.7%

All deviations were within 5%, indicating acceptable consistency in the experimental results. The deviation in the results may be due to subtle differences in the packing of the reactor and the assembly of the setup. In addition, the overall process of lifting the thermocouples for each axial position may also contribute to these deviations.

9 Conclusions

This research aimed to investigate the heat transfer characteristics of structured packed beds with Periodic Open Cellular structures (POCS), Triply Periodic Minimal Surface (TPMS) structures, and monoliths. By exploring these structures in the context of methanol synthesis via CO₂ hydrogenation, the study aimed to improve heat transfer and process intensification for small-scale, distributed chemical production systems. Recognizing the importance of such advancements for achieving sustainable energy goals, the research focused on how variables like cell size, geometry, porosity, and wall contact affect thermal management, particularly as it applies to catalytic reactions with both exothermic and endothermic steps.

The experimental findings from structured packed beds, conducted as dedicated heat transfer tests, reveal several key insights:

- 1. Effect of Lattice Geometry and Flow Rate on Heat Transfer:** The heat transfer coefficient increased with flow rate for all lattice structures, but the rate of increase varied across different geometries. Diamond lattice and TPMS diamond matrix structures showed sharper increases compared to the diamond TPMS network and TPMS gyroid matrix, likely due to their more complex geometry and higher tortuosity, which boost turbulence and convective heat transfer. This factor is crucial in selecting geometric designs for catalytic reactors.
- 2. Role of Wall Contact:** Wall contact was identified as a key factor influencing heat transfer efficiency. Structures with poor wall contact exhibited lower heat transfer coefficients, even lower than traditional monolith designs. Improved wall contact significantly enhanced heat transfer, but after reaching a certain level of wall contact, the improvement plateaued, highlighting the importance of optimized fabrication techniques and reactor design.
- 3. Comparison of Experimental and Theoretical Values:** Theoretical predictions of the airside heat transfer coefficient, based on a one-dimensional heat transfer model, showed a 30% margin of error compared to experimental values, especially for structures with smaller cell sizes. The closer alignment for smaller cells suggests that compact geometries offer better matches with theoretical models due to reduced boundary layer effects and enhanced conductive pathways.
- 4. Design Considerations for Process Intensification:** The study demonstrated that structured packed beds with optimal geometry and porosity could significantly improve heat transfer, which is essential for effective process intensification. Smaller cell sizes substantially

enhance conductive heat transfer, while larger cell sizes result in a lower heat transfer coefficient. In general, TPMS structures exhibited better heat transfer properties than POCS structures. Although further research is needed, the diamond matrix showed better heat transfer than the gyroid matrix with the same number of cells. Optimized structures in decentralized reactors could offer an efficient path for integrating chemical production with renewable energy sources.

These findings provide a strong foundation for future work on catalyst support design, especially for small-scale reactors focused on sustainable chemical production. While methanol synthesis was used as the model reaction, the insights gained here are broadly applicable to catalytic processes requiring effective thermal management.

Clearly, these structures outperform simple packed beds in terms of heat transfer and process intensification. A deeper analysis of node and strut sizes, as well as material selection, would be beneficial for further optimization. Additionally, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis could offer a more comprehensive understanding of flow patterns and their impact on performance. Further experimental testing under reactor conditions, particularly in reactive environments and with different catalyst sizes, and accounting for pressure drop across catalytic beds is essential to validate and expand upon these findings. This combined approach has the potential to advance the development of more efficient, decentralized chemical reactors.

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APPENDIX

A: Structure Images

Figure A1. Microscopic view of diamond cell lattice structures with cell size: (a) 2.8 mm (b) 3.4 mm (c) 4.6 mm (d) 2.8 mm with outer wall

Figure A2. Microscopic view of (a) Honeycomb Monolith (b) Cubic Cell

Figure A3. Microscopic view of TPMS structures: (a) Diamond Network (b) Diamond Matrix (c) Diamond Matrix (d) Gyroid Matrix

Figure A4. Honeycomb Monolith machine cut for packed bed sample

B: Temperature Profiles and Heat transfer coefficients

(a)

(b)

Fig B1 Temperature profiles of 2.8 mm diamond cell lattice structure at radial positions (a) 5 mm and (b) 10 mm

(a)

(b)

Figure B2 Temperature profile at $G=1.303 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$ for diamond cell lattice with cell size (a) 3.4 mm and (c) 4.6 mm

Table B1: Comparison of heat transfer coefficients for various structures

S.No.	Sample	U_{overall} (W/m²K)	U_{air} (W/m²K)
1	Packed	71.54337	82.95686
2	Diamond 2.8x2.8x2.8 (empty)	89.17492	107.6329
3	Monolith	115.8923	149.1286
4	Diamond 2.8 mm	166.8948	245.7774
5	Diamond 3.4 mm	145.9228	202.8454
6	Diamond 4.6 mm	128.5566	170.7768
7	Diamond 2.8 mm outer wall	174.216	261.9912
8	Cubic 4.0 mm	132.1843	177.2384
9	Diamond network	155.9801	222.8166
10	Diamond matrix 4.3 mm	210.911	354.8289
11	Diamond matrix 6 mm	147.8564	206.6012
12	Gyroid matrix	167.3122	246.6837